

Comparing Attraction-Based and Groove-Based Haptic Line Guidance

Henric Andersson¹[0009-0007-0487-429X], Pernilla Josefsson²[0000-0002-5407-0667], Jonas Moll³[0000-0002-4772-4730], and Eva-Lotta Sallnäs Pysander¹[0000-0002-6843-867X]

¹ KTH Royal Institute of Technology, 100 44 Stockholm, Sweden

² Södertörn University, 141 89 Huddinge, Sweden

³ Örebro University, 701 82 Örebro, Sweden

Abstract. Haptic guidance can support movement in grounded stylus tasks, but its effectiveness depends on predictability and intention-alignment of rendered forces. This experimental study compares two common strategies: attraction-based guidance and groove-based guidance, applied to a graph line in an 11×11 planar grooved grid implemented in CHAI3D. Eight participants have completed a follow-the-dot task requiring them to enter, exit, cross and follow the graph line. Performance measures included time to target and movement precision. Preliminary findings show that attraction-based guidance enables slightly faster performance, and that groove-based guidance yields more precise movements. Data collection is ongoing.

Keywords: Haptic guidance · Line guidance · Virtual fixtures

1 Introduction

Two common strategies for haptic line guidance are attraction-based and groove-based guidance. Attraction-based methods, often implemented as virtual fixtures, pull the interaction point toward a target line [2, 4, 5]. Groove-based methods instead render the line as a concave channel that restricts movement [6, 4, 1]. For haptic graph exploration, this is a central design issue because mathematical lines have no physical thickness and must therefore be rendered through geometry or force fields. However, the forces rendered must be interpretable, predictable, and aligned with the user’s intention, otherwise they may reduce performance or be resisted by users [3]. Fritz and Barner [2] showed that attraction-based guidance can help users find and follow graph lines, while Yu et al. [6] argued that concave channel-like renderings are better suited for grounded single-point devices than raised renderings.

This study is also motivated by earlier work by Sallnäs et al. [5], where graphs were rendered as magnetic lines for visually impaired users. Although the magnetic force helped users find lines, it also disturbed broader exploration of the coordinate system, especially when crossing lines. To our knowledge, attraction-based and groove-based approaches have not been systematically compared previously. This gap is addressed by comparing groove-based and attraction-based

guidance in a structured planar environment with a grooved grid and an embedded graph line. Movement performance was investigated with respect to time and precision when performing a follow-the-dot task.

RQ: How do groove-based and attraction-based guidance differ in movement performance across different interaction phases?

This work aims to provide early insight into how different haptic guidance strategies support interaction in structured tasks. The results reported are preliminary.

2 Method

At the time of writing, 8 students from three different Swedish universities have participated; data collection is ongoing toward a target of 24. Participants were 18+, with normal or corrected-to-normal vision, sufficient motor ability to use a stylus, and fluency in Swedish or English. Written informed consent was obtained.

The study used a 3D Systems Touch stylus device with an application built in CHAI3D (1 kHz haptics, 60 Hz graphic loops). The environment consisted of a planar 11×11 grooved XY grid with a single graph line crossing it at 45° . The graph line was always shown visually as a thin yellow line. Two graph-line guidance conditions were compared. In the groove-based condition, the line was rendered as a narrow haptic channel, slightly deeper than the grid lines. In the attraction-based condition, the line generated an attractive force field within a capture radius. The background grid grooves were identical across all conditions.

Participants performed a standardized follow-the-dot task. The stylus tip was displayed as a small light blue sphere and the current target as a small dark blue sphere at a grid intersection. Each movement was a straight segment along a grid groove. The target sequences were designed to evoke four interaction phases in equal proportions: entering the graph line, exiting it, crossing it, and following it. Targets were confirmed using a 200 ms dwell.

A between-subjects design with four participants assigned to each condition was used. After completing an identical training block, participants completed four test trials within their assigned guidance condition. The presentation order of trials was counterbalanced across participants to minimize trial-specific order effects. The study had two co-primary outcomes: time to target and movement precision. Movement precision was measured as total travel distance in the XY plane, as a proxy for movement efficiency. A secondary outcome was the average deviation from the optimal straight path in the XY plane. Repeated observations were collapsed into participant-level, interaction-phase-specific means, from which condition-level descriptive statistics were computed.

3 Results and Discussion

The reported descriptives are means and standard deviations aggregated at the condition level. Preliminary results suggest that attraction-based guidance en-

abled slightly faster performance, particularly when entering the graph line ($M = 0.51$, $SD = 0.09$, vs. $M = 0.62$, $SD = 0.10$ for groove-based guidance) and when following it ($M = 0.62$, $SD = 0.08$, vs. $M = 0.75$, $SD = 0.14$). In contrast, groove-based guidance yielded more precise movements across all interaction phases, reflected in both shorter path lengths and lower average deviation from the optimal line. One participant in the attraction-based condition often moved along the x- and y-axis grooves toward the next target instead of following the graph line. This is evident in the descriptives for the follow-line phase, where both the mean and standard deviation of the Deviation metric were markedly higher for attraction-based guidance ($M = 1.31$, $SD = 0.95$) than for groove-based guidance ($M = 0.50$, $SD = 0.15$).

Table 1. Mean values (with standard deviations in parentheses) for each metric and interaction phase under groove-based and attraction-based guidance. Time is reported in seconds and distance in mm.

Metric	Interaction phase	Groove-based M(SD)	Attraction-based M(SD)
Time (s)	Enter line	0.62 (0.10)	0.51 (0.09)
Time (s)	Exit line	0.67 (0.12)	0.66 (0.27)
Time (s)	Cross line	0.88 (0.15)	0.80 (0.29)
Time (s)	Follow line	0.75 (0.14)	0.62 (0.08)
Length (mm)	Enter line	9.56 (0.13)	11.07 (1.53)
Length (mm)	Exit line	9.71 (0.19)	12.72 (3.09)
Length (mm)	Cross line	18.27 (0.35)	20.30 (2.32)
Length (mm)	Follow line	13.41 (0.33)	15.35 (2.11)
Deviation (mm)	Enter line	0.34 (0.04)	0.51 (0.25)
Deviation (mm)	Exit line	0.41 (0.09)	0.58 (0.33)
Deviation (mm)	Cross line	0.43 (0.06)	0.52 (0.23)
Deviation (mm)	Follow line	0.50 (0.15)	1.31 (0.95)

4 Open Research Questions and Interdisciplinary Exchange

Our preliminary work on haptic guidance that supports movement in tasks involving grounded stylus devices suggests that attraction-based guidance enabled slightly faster performance, and that groove-based guidance yielded more precise movements across all interaction phases, reflected in both shorter path lengths and lower average deviation from the optimal line. However, their application and perceptual impact for visually impaired users remain open questions.

Acknowledgments. This study was funded by The Swedish Research Council (grant number 2023-01012).

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

References

1. Alaçam, Ö., Acartürk, C., Habel, C., Marcus, A.: Haptic exploration patterns in virtual line-graph comprehension. In: Design, User Experience, and Usability: Users and Interactions, pp. 403–414. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, Springer International Publishing, Cham (2015)
2. Fritz, J.P., Barner, K.E.: Design of a haptic graphing system. In: Langton, A. (ed.) Proceedings of the RESNA '96 Annual Conference: Exploring New Horizons ... Pioneering the 21st Century. pp. 158–160. RESNA Press, Salt Lake City, Utah (1996)
3. Mugge, W., Kuling, I.A., Brenner, E., Smeets, J.B.J.: Haptic guidance needs to be intuitive not just informative to improve human motor accuracy. *PloS one* **11**(3), e0150912 (2016)
4. Paneels, S., Roberts, J.C.: Review of designs for haptic data visualization. *IEEE transactions on haptics* **3**(2), 119–137 (2010)
5. Sallnäs, E.L., Moll, J., Ljunggren, L., Sikberg, M.: Virtuella lärmiljöer för grupparbete mellan seende och svårt synskadade elever [virtual learning environments for group work between sighted and severely visually impaired pupils]. Final report 2019-04591, Vinnova (2021), in Swedish
6. Yu, W., Ramloll, R., Brewster, S., Ridel, B.: Exploring computer-generated line graphs through virtual touch. In: 2001 6th International Symposium on Signal Processing and Its Applications. vol. 1, pp. 72–75 vol.1. IEEE (2001)